

GreenSoul: An IoT platform for empowering users' energy efficiency in public buildings

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Abstract. The GreenSoul (GS) framework aims to provide a low-cost energy-efficient Information and Communications Technology (ICT) platform which seamlessly augments a traditional public-use building with a set of assets (apps, interactive interfaces, device adaptors, smart meters and a Decision Support Engine), which mediate in the interactions of users with their environments and the energy consuming devices or systems present in them. GreenSoul envisions public use buildings as ecosystems of GreenSoul-ed devices which cooperate with other devices, standard Smart Meters and, very importantly, with eco-educated and eco-aware users to minimize the unnecessary energy consumption. GS architecture is supported by a socio-economic behavioural model, which aids on behaviour understanding to turn energy consuming devices into active pro-sustainability agents that manifest to their surrounding users how well or badly they are being manipulated (energy-wise), offer tips about how to use them more efficiently and even adapt their own functioning to avoid energy waste.

Keywords: IoT Framework, Sustainability, Energy-efficiency, Internet-of-Things, Edge Computing, Semantic Interoperability.

1 Introduction

On 25th October 2012, the EU adopted the Directive 2012/27/EU on energy efficiency (known as the Energy Efficiency Directive [1]), a significant milestone in promoting EU energy efficiency objectives. Specifically, the EU 20-20-20 by 2020 energy target commands *a*) a reduction of the greenhouse gas emissions by 20% compared to 1990, *b*) to increase the share of renewable energy sources in energy consumption to 20% and *c*) a 20% increase in energy efficiency. On 2016, the Commission proposed an update including a new 30% energy efficiency target for 2030.

The GreenSoul (GS) project¹ aims to surpass the objectives of energy efficiency targets imposed from the EU with an ICT platform empowered by a novel socio-economic and behavioural model. This model aims at guiding and aiding more eco-aware practices on people, devices and buildings. Specifically, the key contribution of GreenSoul will be to transform both the energy consumption practices of workers of public buildings and the operation mode of the energy consuming devices that they interact with (e.g. coffee-makers, PCs, printers, etc.) at their working environments. GS's view is that it is possible to surpass EU targets providing a true technological collaboration among people (employees), devices of private and collective use and buildings.

The need for this multi-level and collaborative approach is two-fold. On the one side, it lays on the growing issue of misusing energy consuming devices and systems in buildings, as one of the main sources of unnecessary energy consumption. Notably, they account for 40% of energy end-use in the EU [2] and making them more efficient is, therefore, paramount. On the other side, households have already been targeted successfully either by the academia and public administrations. However, public buildings or buildings of public use still demand more attention. In this scenario, the overall goal of this work is to present the conceptual architecture of the GS platform.

2 Related Work

Many factors influence consumer behaviour and practices. Technological developments, considerations of the general economic situation, age, social norms, belief systems and cultural traits, marketing strategies: all play an important role in defining what we consider a normal way of life. On the one hand, a recent research suggests that consumer preferences change over time [5], and consequently the focus should shift from the consumer behaviour *per se* (which tends to imply emphasis on individual or group preferences) to how different consumption practices take hold in the society. On the other hand, there are different ways to deliver feedback and expect an appropriate reaction to them as reviewed in [6] and meta-analysed in [7, 8]. However, the key lies in combining different measures to achieve substantial energy savings up to 20% [15].

Research on energy efficiency points to the fact that the link between measures, i.e. a wider deployment of Smart Meters, and behaviour analytics is crucially important because there is evidence to suggest that technical interventions alone have lower impact and are more cost-ineffective if carried out in isolation, i.e. without any accompanying program designed to encourage behaviour change [6]. In this context, research into behavioural change [9] aims to identify the educational, social, psychological and economic drivers underlying energy consumption patterns, and to define and evaluate measures – such as policy initiatives and incentive systems – that may influence those patterns in desired ways. With regards to public buildings, an additional problem is that their tenants, employees or visitors do not have the same aware-

¹ <http://www.greensoul-h2020.eu>

ness and motivations regarding energy consumption as they may have in their homes. Workers are usually unaware of the actual electricity bill of their organisation and about how their often unconscious misuse of appliances is contributing towards increasing energy consumption and thus CO₂ emissions. Indeed, a report surveying the buildings sector across 9 countries [10] recognised the role of occupant behaviour as having ‘as much impact on energy consumption as the efficiency of equipment’.

GS resembles some previously reported architectures which follow the edge computing paradigm [16] and feature similar aspects as the GS framework [3, 4].

3 GreenSoul Solution Architecture

The architecture proposed for this project is divided into three layers according to its physical deployment as can be observed in Figure 1: 1) *Device Layer*; 2) *Building Layer*; and 3) *Cloud Layer*. Each of these layers and the components and modules behind them are described in this Section. The communication interfaces, protocols and databases selected, and interdependencies among the devised GS architecture components are also detailed. An overview of the GS components is listed below:

3.1 Multi-Sensorial Network

Various sensors are installed inside the building premises and monitor raw data regarding current building operation (e.g. energy consumption or occupancy). Dedicated Device Managers (software) collect and pre-process these data and transforms them in GIM-compliant event messages. This information is spread to the upper layers of GS architecture through the Middleware. Actuators are also utilized in order to facilitate load control mechanisms within pilot buildings, when such actions are necessary.

Additional components are the GS-ed Things and GS adaptors which are described in Section 5. These are new electronic devices developed in the context of the GreenSoul attach-able to appliances or electrical equipment of collective use at pilot’s buildings (e.g. printers, coffee-makers, outlets or power strips). The purpose of such adaptors is to optimise usage of the mentioned appliances and electrical equipment.

3.2 Middleware

The interoperability needs, derived mostly from the variety of sensors, actuators and software systems installed, are tackled in the GreenSoul architecture by a well-known Internet of Things (IoT) middleware called LinkSmart² (right side of Figure 1). Its main function is to facilitate seamless integration of GS-ed devices and legacy sensors infrastructure with GS software applications. LinkSmart includes a Device Manager component that provides the capabilities for heterogeneous devices virtualization through a common interface, for easier access to the lower Device Layer, independently of the technology used. Besides, through the Event Manager component, it

² <http://www.linksmart.eu/>

provides a publish/subscribe service, for enabling events-based communication, i.e. enabling publishing and distribution to those components which have subscribed to receive them.

3.3 Decision Support System

The GreenSoul Decision Support Engine includes the set of instructions and algorithmic processes that are needed to deploy intelligent control and persuasion mechanisms to the devices and users in the system. In order for these mechanisms to work properly, the GS DSS obtains dynamic data through the Middleware and static data through the GIM Database. Further explanation of the module operation is available at Section 6.1.

3.4 GIM-compliant Databases

Static and real-time information from GS-ed devices will be stored in non-relational databases which are compliant with the GreenSoul Information Model (GIM). These databases have their own APIs to connect and gather information from various GS-ed devices and provide such information to other services. Further details on the GIM ontology structure for data storing can be found in Section 4.

3.5 Visualization Interfaces

The components of the Cloud layer provide enriched graphical representation of energy-related data both in terms of individual and group-based device use, as well as a distribution channel for the persuasion messages from GreenSoul solution. Access to such information will be provided through all web-enabled devices (PC's, tablets, smartphones etc.). Energy-consumption data captured, stored and processed, per device and user, is accessible from these interfaces towards providing a user-friendly portal to analyse and display required information for educational and informative purposes, on devices that are being accessed daily in conformity with agreed behavioural change and modification processes and protocols in buildings where GreenSoul is deployed.

Figure 1. GreenSoul Reference Architecture

4 GIM Information Modelling and Information Collection

A common information model is essential when interconnection between heterogeneous resources is required. GIM introduces a shared vocabulary of well-defined entities, attributes and objects that provide interoperability through different information sharing protocols and make information in-between various GS components easily accessible. Both static and dynamic data are translated and presented in an understandable and uniform way, so as to be used from all GS components.

Static information includes constant contextual data that have been modelled in a GIM compliant manner to describe elements such as the building architectural map, devices location, sensors and so on. Furthermore, dynamic aspects related to the building are also included, containing among others, energy consumption, indoor environmental information, occupancy, and users' interactions with the building's assets. All that information is supported by a hybrid storage repository within the GIM by employing both InfluxDB and MongoDB for handling time-dependent information and large amounts of static and historical events (document-dependent) respectively.

Access to such data under a robust and unobtrusive, yet fast and complete manner is achieved through a RESTful-based application programming interface (API) that allows through a series of services over HTTP to insert, updated, delete and retrieve stored knowledge.

Figure 2. High-level GIM schema

The definition of GIM has been produced in the form of XML schemas [11], which is one of the most widely-used formats for sharing structured information. More specifically, it provides a globally acceptable language for transmission of energy-related information. Another advantage is that semantics stemming from XML schemas can be easily translated in various ontologies (i.e. RDF/XML) through simple XSL transformations. The high level architecture of GIM is depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 3. GIM: Information Model and Event entities

The two core elements of this architecture are the *GSIInformationModel* entity and the *Event* entity, both described in Figure 3. The former includes objects related to static information such as the building systems, sensors, devices, users, persuasion strategies, settings, etc. The latter, specifies objects regarding dynamic information, such as sensors' obtained measurements, updated evaluated data, selection of an optimised persuasive strategy for certain groups of workers and so on.

GIM modelling was conceived having in mind the interoperability. This is the reason why open and well-known standards were included to cover several components of the final GS Data model. Specifically, parts of gbXML³ are utilized to facilitate the building shell modelling (construction/material/windows etc.) and environmental context elements (weather, campus structure around the building etc.). Also, obXML [12] protocol is used to model occupants' behaviour inside the building, which is derived from the Drivers-Needs-Actions-Systems (DNAS) modelling framework.

According to the application and in alignment with the interoperable GIM approach, there are additional variables/modes for persuasion mechanisms for energy efficiency improvement that are already partially integrated and that can be further improved.

5 GreenSoul-ed Things

A set of everyday electrical devices of collective use will be selected from the pilot sites (especially those with a high-energy consumption rate) to attach adaptors to them that transform them into GreenSoul-ed Things (GS-ed Things). These adaptors enhance the bare equipment that can be found in a workplace with not only local intelligence and remote actuations mechanisms but also providing persuasive interfaces to interact with their users in the environments, enabling the use of Edge/Fog-

³ <http://www.gbxml.org/>

computing techniques [13] for a more effective decision making where and when it is needed. According to the analysis carried out on the initial phases of the project’s pilot sites (see Table 1 for a short description of them), the selected electrical devices to be enriched are coffee-makers, elevators, printers, desk’s power strips, lighting and HVAC systems. As can be observed, these devices are used at three different levels: *individual* (desk’s power strips), group or *work-team-level* (coffee-makers and printers), and *building-level* (lighting, HVAC system and elevators).

GS-ed Things fulfil a two-fold purpose: *a)* provide users with feedback through physical and ambient cues that help them understand and learn how to optimise their interaction with the augmented devices and systems in an energy-wise manner and *b)* ensure remote controllability to enable convenient energy-modes and practices, e.g. remote switching off/on, reaching ideal temperatures, and so forth as per the device decision trees’ tables.

GS-ed Things are composed of several Open Source Hardware and Software components which enable them to connect directly to the LinkSmart middleware through HTTP operations. GS-ed Things feature Internet connection, so they can be directly accessed from everywhere through LinkSmart, being their resources exposed following RESTful principles. Furthermore, adaptors attached to everyday things provide embedded current sensors to measure energy consumption, helping to monitor the current operational status of the appliances that they are connected to.

6 GreenSoul Decision Support System (DSS)

6.1 Main Control Algorithm

DSS supports a set of operations for monitoring and control the building assets (e.g. lights, HVAC, appliances, etc.). The main goal is to maximize energy efficiency while respecting occupants’ comfort.

The overall flow diagram of the DSS operation is depicted in Figure 4. The building is divided into lighting zones (including one or more sets of lights) and thermal zones (including one or more HVAC units) based on topology and usage. Appliances, such as monitors and printers, are also considered as a separate category. The purpose of this module is to calculate the most energy efficient states of the system, while requiring minimum comfort sacrifice from the end-users; for each lighting/thermal zone, the optimal operational state of lighting and HVAC devices is computed respectively.

Figure 4. Overall flow diagram of the DSS operation

The aforementioned process can be seen in more detail in Figure 5. At first, the module receives the current occupancy status from the occupancy extraction mechanism [14] in order to decide its next actions. If the zone is empty, the system automatically turns off any lights that are on. The same stands true for the HVAC systems, but only after checking the occupancy prediction [17] for the next minutes. In the case when there are people in the zone, the system resides on the analytics engine to evaluate occupants' visual/thermal comfort. More specifically, current environmental data are obtained from the multi-sensorial network (luminance measurements for lighting, indoor air, temperature and humidity for HVAC,). These values, along with contextual data related with the specific zone (profiles of users, building spatial information etc.) are used to extract an initial estimation of the preferable comfort value for each zone. Then, previous end-users' corrective actions on defining their preferable luminance/temperature settings are taken into account in order to re-calculate the *comfort threshold* (mean of visual/thermal comfort) of the zone that users consider as acceptable.

6.2 Core (Simulation) Engine

In a later stage, the core DSS engine simulates various states of the system devices, while respecting the comfort threshold of the zone. Various combinations of operation modes are examined (e.g. combination of open light units, blinds' position etc.) and ultimately, the most energy efficient one is chosen. Finally, having calculated the corresponding increase/decrease in luminance/temperature which should be derived by each light/HVAC unit, the relative *setpoints* can be sent to the Persuasion Engine.

Figure 5. Flow diagram for each visual/thermal zone

6.3 Persuasion Engine

The Persuasion Engine has been designed to implement a novel socio-economic self-learning module, which would be able to estimate the best persuasion strategy to be deployed per each cluster of users. The module achieves this by receiving the list of actions per device and zone from the CoreEngine and collecting socio-economic factors (e.g. age, preferences, etc.) and persuasion techniques that have already been identified and stored in the GIM database. Then, it assigns weighted factors to these criteria in order to match user profiles against their corresponding strategies. Eventually, a stochastic and self-learning mechanism is adopted (through a Reinforcement Learning algorithm); the user receives the deployed persuasion strategy and either responds successfully or chooses to ignore it. This success status feedback causes the engine to re-evaluate its selected strategy and achieve better future results.

7 Use Cases

The use case scenarios introduced in this section are focused on the application of the GreenSoul framework in multiple tertiary non-controllable environments (see Table 1) towards controlling and leading end-users' energy consumption. By providing a "greener" education through the proper messages and incentives, enriched with effective persuasion and motivation mechanisms adapted to the users' profiles, occupants' energy-related awareness is expected to rise to levels that will have (in)direct impact to the building's consumption. It is our ultimate goal to affect and promote a change in the behaviour of the people who populate shared spaces in public buildings, which can be rather cumbersome since currently eco-friendly behaviours are based entirely on individual belief and effort, and the link between actions and results, regarding energy consumption, is not always very clear.

Table 1. Pilot Scenarios for the GreenSoul framework.

Pilot	Max. Num. of Occupants	Country
Institute of Cartography of Andalusia	~200	Seville, Spain
IT of the University of Deusto.	92	Bilbao, Spain
Pilea-Hortiatis Municipality Hall	25	Thessaloniki, Greece
Haywards Heath	22	Sussex, UK
Allia Ltd	~300	Cambridge, UK
Energy & Innovation Centre	12	Weiz, Austria

Energy, social and financial related human behaviour models are formulated for each pilot premises taking into consideration behavioural aspects such as age, education, family, eco-awareness and so on, combined with information extracted by the equipment installed (i.e. smart meters) filtered through static data already modelled in GIM (i.e. positioning – gbXML, devices and assets), offering a multi-parameter anal-

ysis that provides the proper weights for two aspects: a) creating the comfort level inputs for the DSS, and b) assign incentive strategies to the proper building population.

Namely, two specific uses cases that can best describe the added-value offered by the GreenSoul solution are described in the following sections: a Lighting and an HVAC scenarios as mappings to the GS-architecture.

7.1 Lighting Scenario

Eve, Maria and Roger work together in the same office, located in building fully equipped with blinds, lights, and an HVAC system that keeps the temperature of the room at the desired level. At noon, they decide to turn off the HVAC and open the windows so that fresh air circulates inside the office. By the end of the day, Maria is the last person to leave the office. She has closed the windows but has forgotten to switch off the lights. After one minute she is informed through an application on her Smartphone that she has forgotten the lights on. The application tries to convince Maria through persuasion techniques to return back and switch off the lights. There is a time-limit of 10 minutes set by the application, in order for Maria to react as soon as possible. Finally, Maria gets convinced to return back and switch the lights off.

Within this scenario, the GreenSoul Device Network would be composed of the light bulbs, LEDs lamps, corridor lights, energy smart meters, blinds, sensors (presence, motion entry/exit). Data such as the number of persons in the room and the amount of irradiance are constantly sent to the LinkSmart middleware. The DSS receives the data from the middleware and sends information to the room occupants through visual prompts to make people aware about their real-time actions by displaying indoor irradiance conditions inside the office, giving energy advice to the users regarding the use of lights in each room, displaying notifications for lighting misuse through applications on the users' PCs or mobile phones, or providing data about the quantity of energy that can be saved by just decreasing temperature some degrees through the thermostat. The ultimate purpose is to persuade users to follow a more energy efficient behaviour. In addition, the DSS can directly actuate over the lighting units, by turning them off when needed. Figure 6 shows how the components of the Lighting Scenario are mapped to the Greensoul architecture.

Figure 6. Mapping of the Lighting Scenario to the GS architecture

7.2 HVAC Scenario

Similarly to the first use case scenario, the HVAC scenario follows a slightly different approach, mainly due to thermal inertia.

Giannis, Nick and Steve work together in the same office, located in a remote building fully equipped with a HVAC system that keeps the temperature of the room at the desired level, and various sensors for measuring required real-time data (e.g. temperature, humidity, consumption, etc.). It is a sunny summer day and the office is rather hot, therefore they close the windows and turn on the HVAC to lower the temperature of the room. At noon, they decide to go for lunch but they usually forget to turn off or raise the temperature set point of the HVAC system. However, based on knowledge extracted by the GS behavioural models, the system after anticipating such behaviour, issues a message saying that if they are gone for more than 15', they should turn off the HVAC or raise the set point for 2 degrees if they are going to be back in less than that. The application tries to convince Giannis and Nick (that are more fond of such tactics) by explaining the reasons behind the two different actions as well as the merits, through appropriate persuasion techniques. If there is no response from them, a second message is sent, as in the lighting scenario case. Finally, Giannis regulates the set point to a higher temperature and thus reducing the HVAC power consumption.

The components and methods used within this scenario are similar to the previous description (see Section 7.1), utilising only different kind of real-time information and decision making logic. Furthermore, as already explained, the GreenSoul Behavioural models provide the necessary information for selecting the optimal time and user for applying the persuasion techniques.

8 Conclusions and Future Work

In this paper an innovative ICT architecture has been presented following the Edge Computing paradigm to foster behavioural change towards a more lenient use of primary energy resources in a building of public use. To this end, the architecture consists of three layers that loosely resemble their physical localization: the device layer, the building layer and the cloud layer. The main innovation resides in the presence of the GreenSould-ed devices. These devices will be the cornerstone to retrieve process and foster behavioural change in an autonomous and resilient way. Finally, two use cases have been described and mapped to the aforementioned architecture. This paper only covers the overall architecture without taking into consideration the best option to develop its components. In this sense, the following steps will include an in depth analysis of different middleware options, including not only technical aspects (like performance) but also social ones (ease of use or community friendliness). Furthermore we envisage to develop a comparison between different algorithmic strategies to create the forecasting module and the DSS.

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